

Types And Causes Of Errors In Essay Writing: Error Analysis Of Students' Essays At Ssc And O-Level In Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 23,2025</p> <p>Accepted: September 24,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Comparative study, Essay writing, Error analysis, O levels & SSC</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17194888</p>	<p><i>This comparative study analyses the errors in writing essays in English by the students of Secondary School Certificate (SSC/Matriculation) and the General Certificate of Education-Ordinary level (GCE-O-Level) in the Province Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) in Pakistan. The population of the study has included the students and English Language teachers of SSC and O-Level in KP through Random Sampling Technique. The study is descriptive in nature. The data has been collected in the form of written essays and through structured interviews from the students and teachers respectively. The data is analyzed descriptively by employing Corder model of Error Analysis (1967), and the frequency of various types of errors has also been discussed. The study has revealed that O-Level students are comparatively competent in essay writing than the SSC level students as SSC students committed more errors in writing essays as compared to O-Level students in Pakistan. The findings of the study reveals that ELT teachers in Pakistan need to adopt effective teaching methodologies for teaching essay writing skills and are suggested to provide proper feedback to their students in order to make them aware of the errors and the possible causes for committing such errors. The findings of the study will facilitate the teaching-learning process of essay writing in English in Pakistan.</i></p>

Introduction

Essay writing skills assist students in performing well at the higher level of education and also in professional life (Nunan, 2001 & Dovey, 2010). Secondary School Certificate (SSC) and the General Certificate of Education-Ordinary level (GCE-O-Level) are the two parallel systems of education functioning in Pakistan. The SSC system of education is providing education to the common people while the GCE O-Level system of education is for the elite class. At these levels, English is considered the most important subject in the curriculum (Naeem, 2011). According to Harris (1969), Listening, Reading, Speaking and Writing are the four basic skills of a language. In the views of Adas and Bakir (2013), writing is a complex and complicated task and resultantly, the most difficult to acquire in all languages that exist. Moreover, Emmons (2005) labels writing as a "hard work" (as cited in Awg Nik, Hamzah & Rafidee, 2010), and essay writing is no exception.

Sources of Errors

The Study conducted by Richard (1971) shows three main sources of errors which are given below:

1. Interference Errors: such errors occur when elements from one language are used while writing another language.
2. Intra-lingual Errors: Such errors occur as a result of faulty generalisation, incomplete application of rules as well as failure to learn those conditions under which the rules are applied.
3. Developmental Errors: Such errors are the result of the learner attempt to form a hypothesis about the target language on the basis of deficient experience.

Causes of Errors

According to Norrish (1983), there are the following three major causes of errors which are carelessness, first language interference, and translation (as cited in Hasyim, 2002).

1. Carelessness: Carelessness takes place when the learner loses interest or motivation. This loss of interest is not solely the fault of the learner rather the style of presentation also has an impact on it.
2. First Language: According to him, a language is learned through habit formation. When new habits are acquired, the old ones interfere with them. Such a cause is known as first language interference.
3. Translation: This happens when the learner tries to translate the sentences of first language into the target language verbatim. This is the most common cause of error.

According to Richards (1971), the causes of error are classified into: i) overgeneralization, ii) deficient use of rules, iii) false concepts hypothesized, and iv) ignorance of rule restriction (as cited in Hasyim, 2002).

Steps to Errors Analysis

As stated by Ellis (1997), there are four steps to Error Analysis: identification of errors, description of errors, and explanation of errors and evaluation of errors. He also differentiates errors from mistakes. According to him, errors occur because of the gap in the learner's knowledge while mistakes occur because of lapses in performance. The learner cannot perform in a particular situation what they know (as cited in Ahmed, Amin & Qureshi, 2020).

Error Analysis is a systematic procedure used by both teachers and researchers. This process involves the following steps: Collection of learners' language samples, identifying errors in samples, classifying the errors according to their nature and finally evaluating the errors (Keshavarz, 2015). Corder (1975) proposed several steps for Error Analysis, which is as under.

1. Sample Collection of learner language
2. Errors Identification
3. Errors Description
4. Errors Explanation
5. Errors Evaluation

Literature Review

Crystal (2003) defines 'Error Analysis' as a way to identify, classify and interpret the unacceptable forms produced by a foreign language learner by using the principles and procedures offered by linguists. This field was established by Corder and his colleagues in the 1970s. The findings of several researches show that learners commit errors because of the misunderstanding of the rules on the part of learners. Error Analysis is a type of linguistic study whose main focus is on the errors that learners make. According to Corder (1967) errors are significant in and of themselves. He states if errors made by the learners are systematically analysed, it will be possible to know the weak areas of the students that need reinforcement in the process of teaching. Corder (1967) makes a distinction between errors and mistakes. According to him both are different phenomena. Errors are those that cannot be self-corrected. They occur when the learning is incomplete or there is a lack of competence, whereas, mistakes can be self-corrected and they occur as a result of the learner failure to perform to their ability. The carelessness of the learners and an error in performance are the causes of mistakes in language use.

Dawson (2008) comments that students commit copious mistakes when writing essays. Such mistakes include the mistakes of spelling, grammar, punctuation and organization. The incorrect use of tense in essay writing is another common mistake that students commit (as cited in Oyedele & Chikwature, 2016). According to Johnson (1985), students exhibit problems in grammar, punctuation, spelling and vocabulary (as cited in Boonpattanaporn, 2007). According to Corder (1967) errors are important because of three reasons. Firstly, they are helpful for teachers by showing the improvement of the students. Secondly, they are helpful to the researchers as they show the strategies used by the learners to learn a language. Thirdly, students can benefit from errors by learning from them. Teachers should know how to correct errors in the writings of students. Some students prefer self-correction while others need peer-correction. There are students who need the corrections made by teachers. Richard (1985) states that error analysis is done for three main reasons: (i) To find out how far one knows a language. (ii) To come to know how a person learns a language. (iii) To get information about common difficulties in learning a language so as to facilitate the process of teaching (as cited in Hasyim, 2002). Al-Haysoni (2012) is of the view that Error Analysis offers teachers to rectify learners' errors, to improve the quality of their teaching, and to concentrate on those areas that need improvement (as cited in Jamil, Majoka & Kamran, 2016).

In the views of Maros, Hua and Salehuddin (2007), the correct use of English grammar poses many difficulties to students in their writing. Frequent errors can be noticed in the correct usage of articles, subject-verb agreement, and also in the copula 'be'. Therefore, materials for teaching and teaching practices within and outside the classroom should cope with the existing problems of students in their written discourse. Nirmala (2008) claims that students at SSC level show poor proficiency in writing. They face problems with the usage of tenses, prepositions, spelling and punctuation (As cited in Fatima & Akbar, 2017). The findings of the study conducted in Pakistan by Ahmed, Amin and Qureshi (2020) shows that errors committed by the learners in written essays are related mainly to subject-verb and pronoun-antecedent agreement errors, contextual errors, errors in the correct choice of words and spelling errors. They also pointed out errors in the correct use of adverbs, capitalisation, abbreviations, prepositions, articles and possessive nouns.

Being a second language, Pakistani secondary school students encounter copious challenges during mastering the skills of English language. When it comes to writing, they commit multiple grammatical errors, and show weaknesses in using meaningful sentences, subject-verb agreement, the correct verb tense, pronouns, prepositions, articles, number, spelling, capitalisation and word order. If the students do not get awareness about the errors they commit and the remedial steps for addressing such errors, they will keep on producing the same errors. Error Analysis can facilitate the effective teaching and learning of English. The current study is an

attempt to enable the SSC and O-Level students to come to know about the errors they commit in writing English essays and the possible causes for committing such errors. It will also enable the teachers to assist individual students overcoming their language related problems as the ability of learning differs from person to person. The researcher hopes that the findings of this study will be equally beneficial for students and teachers. It will facilitate students in knowing the errors they commit and the causes for such errors. It will also guide teachers to assist their students in overcoming such errors by adopting effective teaching methodologies and practices.

Research Methodology

Population and Sample

The population of the current study comprised the Students and teachers of O-Level and SSC (10th Grade) in the province Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in Pakistan. The sample of the study, comprised of 180 students (120 from SSC level and 60 from O-Level) and 72 teachers (48 from SSC level and 24 from O-Level), were randomly selected from the districts of Peshawar, Mardan and Nowshera, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan.

Data Collection and Analysis

The data was collected in form of written essays and structured interviews. All the 180 students were asked to write essays of 200-250 words on two different topics i.e. my Best Friend and which mobile phone do you like and why? After writing essays on the given topics, Error Analysis as a research tool developed by Corder (1967) was used by the researcher to identify errors committed by the students of both the systems in. This model has three steps i.e. (a) collection of sample error, (b) identification of errors and (c) description of errors. The researcher collected data in the form of written essays from the students. The errors were identified and then described.

Structured interviews of 72 teachers were conducted and their responses were recorded and analysed. The Structured interview was based on the following core questions.

- a. What errors do your students frequently commit in writing essays in English?
- b. What problems do you face while teaching English essay writing skills to your students?
- c. What do you think are the possible causes for the weaknesses in English essay writing of the students?

Their responses were summarised, the frequency of the responses had been described, analysed and discussed respectively.

Analysis and Discussion

Analysis of the SSC and O-Level Students' Written Essays

Table 1. shows the type and frequency of errors committed by the participants of both SSC and O-Level.

SSC Level		O-Level		
Type of Error	Frequency of Errors	Type of Error	Frequency	of Errors
Verb Tense	65	Verb Tense	25	
Sentence Fragment	15	Sentence Fragment	01	
Subject-Verb Agreement	90	Subject-Verb Agreement	27	
Capitalisation	71	Capitalisation	30	
Word Order	16	Word Order	02	
Spelling	111	Spelling	33	
Preposition	24	Preposition	14	
Article	40	Article	05	
Pronoun	24	Pronoun	05	
Number	24	Number	06	
Punctuation	16	Punctuation	20	
Total	496	Total	168	

Table 1 indicates that most of the subjects produced errors in writing correct spellings. It was found the most challenging area for the students of both the levels. However, the students who were studying under O-Level were comparatively efficient in their spelling competency than the students who were studying under SSC

Level. The results of the table show that 111 spelling errors were committed by the students at SSC Level as compared to the students at O-Level who have 33 spelling errors in the written essays. It is also clear from table 1 that subject-verb agreement was the second most difficult area for the students. SSC Level students did 90 whereas O-Level students committed 27 errors in the correct use of subject-verb agreement. It was observed by the researcher that mostly students were found ignorant in using the correct form of verbs with the third person singular pronouns, i.e. he/she/it/Ali etc.

Capitalization was also found a difficult area for the students. Most of the students were found ignorant of the rules of capitalization. 71 capitalization errors were recorded of the students studying at SSC Level while 33 such errors were found in the written essays of the students who were studying at O-Level. Most of the students did not know that every sentence begins with a capital letter and that proper nouns are always capitalized. Resultantly, most of the students began a sentence with a small letter. Some of the students capitalized common nouns. Others have capital letters in the middle of words. Students of both the levels had been found deficient in using the correct verb tense. As per table 1, 65 such errors were found in the written essays of the students at SSC Level while 25 errors were recorded in the written assignments of the students at O-Level. Mostly, subjects were unaware of the rules as how to use the correct form of the verb. They used past tense where present tense was suitable and vice versa. Likewise, students committed errors in the aspect as well. They used progressive aspects where they were not required.

Comparing the errors of both the levels in using 'articles' correctly, it was found that SSC level students committed 40 errors in the use of articles while the errors committed by the students at O-Level were only 05. Table 1 reveals that both SSC and O-Level students had shown weaknesses in the correct use of prepositions, although the number of errors committed by the SSC level students was comparatively greater. 24 errors were committed in the correct use of preposition by the students at SSC level while the errors of the students at O-Level were 14. The students studying at both the levels used prepositions where it was not necessary and omitted where it was indispensable.

According to the table, the number of errors of SSC level students was 24 in the correct use of pronoun and the number of errors of the students at O-Level was 05. It is also clear from the table that 24 errors were present in the written works of SSC level students and 06 errors were made by O-Level students in the correct use of number (singular/plural). SSC level students showed more weaknesses in the right use of number than the students of O-Level. The results of the table further throw light on the order of words. The students enrolled under SSC level produced 16 errors to use the words in a proper order. The number of such errors was 02 when it came to the O-Level students. To put punctuation marks correctly in a sentence was also found equally challenging for the students of both the levels. The students at SSC level made 16 errors in the use of punctuation marks while such errors were 20 in the written essays of O-Level students.

Finally, the results of table 1 indicate that 15 errors were made by the SSC level students because they had used sentence fragments which do not convey a full meaning whereas only 01 such error was recorded in the written essays of the O-Level students. Thus, Table 1 clearly shows that the number of errors committed by the students studying under SSC level system of education was greater than the students who were getting education under O-level system of education. The total errors of the SSC level students were found 496 while the collection of errors of the O-level students was recorded 168 in the written essays.

Examples of Errors

Verb Tense

When learners use a wrong verb form in a sentence, this error is considered as the error in the tense of the verb.

Table 2: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Verb Tense

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	Our families <u>used to</u> Nokia mobile phone.	Our families <u>use</u> Nokia mobile phone.
	02	It is very fast <u>working</u> .	It <u>works</u> very fast.
	03	I proud of him.	I am proud of him.
	04	He <u>is</u> prayer five times a day.	He <u>prays</u> five times a day.
	05	He always <u>spoken</u> true.	He always <u>speaks</u> truth.
O-Level	01	She is the person who <u>will help</u> me when I am down and <u>will make</u> me feel better about myself.	She is the person who <u>helps</u> me when I am down and <u>makes</u> me feel better about myself.
	02	I have never <u>hide</u> anything from my mother.	I have never <u>hid/hidden</u> anything from my mother.
	03	Human beings <u>thoughts</u> about the	Human beings <u>think</u> about the

		blessings of Allah.	blessings of Allah.
	04	A Samsung mobile phone <u>is</u> good features.	A Samsung mobile phone <u>has</u> good features.
	05	Nokia <u>is</u> launched a few years back.	Nokia <u>was</u> launched a few years back.

Sentence Fragment

A group of words that is a part of the larger sentence and which neither stand alone as a complete sentence nor expresses a full idea is known as a sentence fragment. Such fragments lose connection with the main clause and hence are disconnected. They are incomplete in the sense that they either don't possess either a subject or a verb.

Table 3: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Sentence Fragment

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	Always reaches to masjid.	<u>He</u> always reaches masjid on time.
	02	A true advisor and well-wisher.	<u>He is</u> a true advisor and well-wisher of me.
	03	I am proud of his	I am proud of his <u>friendship</u> .
O-Level	01	Life without her would be really for me.	Life without her would be really <u>difficult</u> for me.

Subject- Verb Agreement

A subject must always agree with its antecedent in number (singular or plural) and in gender (masculine/feminine). Singular subjects take singular verbs and plural verbs take plural verbs.

Table 4: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Subject- Verb Agreement

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	He <u>have</u> good habits.	He <u>has</u> good habits.
	02	She <u>wear</u> neat and clean clothes.	She <u>wears</u> neat and clean clothes.
	03	Ali <u>recite</u> the Holy Quran daily.	Ali <u>recites</u> the Holy Quran daily.
	04	Products of Samsung <u>is</u> best.	Products of Samsung <u>are</u> best.
	05	My friend <u>share</u> personal things with me.	My friend <u>shares</u> personal things with me.
O-Level	01	We often <u>goes</u> to restaurants.	We often <u>go</u> to restaurants.
	02	My friend always <u>help</u> me in time of need.	My friend always <u>helps</u> me in time of need.
	03	He <u>live</u> abroad.	He <u>lives</u> abroad.
	04	Everybody <u>need</u> a good friend.	Everybody <u>needs</u> a good friend.
	05	It <u>have</u> a 13 MP camera.	It <u>has</u> a 13 MP camera.

Capitalisation

When the very first letter is written in capital or upper-case letter, this is known as capitalisation. The remaining letters are written in small or lower case.

Table 5: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Capitalisation

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	He is <u>My</u> class fellow.	He is <u>my</u> class fellow.
	02	Man is a <u>Social</u> animal.	Man is a <u>social</u> animal.
	03	He cannot <u>Live</u> without the <u>Company</u> of other human beings.	He cannot <u>live</u> without the <u>company</u> of other human beings.
	04	<u>ali</u> is my best <u>Friend</u> .	<u>Ali</u> is my best <u>friend</u> .
	05	<u>in</u> 2000, Nokia was my favourite mobile phone.	<u>In</u> 2000, Nokia was my favourite mobile phone.
O-Level	01	He likes <u>Beef</u> .	He likes <u>beef</u> .
	02	We use cell phone in our daily <u>Life</u> .	We use cell phone in our daily <u>life</u> .

03	Graham <u>bell</u> invented telephone.	Graham <u>Bell</u> invented telephone.
04	Friends make our <u>Life</u> better.	Friends make our <u>life</u> better.
05	I am thankful to God that <u>he</u> blessed me with a friend.	I am thankful to God that <u>He</u> blessed me with a friend.

Word Order

When words, phrases or clauses are arranged syntactically, this process is referred to as Word Order.

Table 6: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Word Order

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	He is more like brother to me.	He is like my brother.
	02	My friend hobby is painting.	The hobby of my friend is painting.
	03	It was a better mobile phone to other phones.	It was a better mobile phone as compared to other phones.
	04	I am lucky is a good friend.	I am lucky to have a good friend.
	05	He always ready to poor to help him.	He is always ready to help the poor.
O-Level	01	There are new more models mobile phones introduced.	Many new models of mobile phones are introduced.
	02	Smart phones touch screen from the seller like I- Phone by Apple, Galaxy by Samsung introduced.	Touch screen smart phones have been introduced by Apple and Samsung companies.

Spellings

Writing words by putting letters according to the acceptable convention for their formation is called spelling.

Table 7: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Spelling

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	Mobile phone is a source of <u>commuction</u> and a <u>nessicatty</u> of life.	Mobile phone is a source of <u>communication</u> and a <u>necessity</u> of life.
	02	Without mobile phone many people would feel <u>incompulatae</u> .	Without mobile phone many people would feel <u>incomplete</u> .
	03	It has a good <u>layet</u> .	It has a good <u>layout</u> .
	04	I can download <u>difrent</u> kinds of books.	I can download <u>different</u> kinds of books.
	05	He understands things <u>quicly</u> .	He understands things <u>quickly</u> .
O-Level	01	My friend is weak at <u>mathmateics</u> .	My friend is weak at <u>mathematics</u> .
	02	So, I went to the <u>shope</u> .	So, I went to the <u>shop</u> .
	03	<u>Offcorse</u> , I like Nokia mobile phone.	<u>Of course</u> , I like Nokia mobile phone.
	04	He <u>recieved</u> many prizes.	He <u>received</u> many prizes.
	05	He was in <u>criticle</u> situation.	He was in <u>critical</u> situation.

Prepositions

There are some words which show the relationship of nouns or pronouns and other words in sentences. Their function is to link nouns, pronouns as well as phrases to other words in sentences. Such words are known as preposition. Prepositions introduce some words or phrases which are called the object of the preposition. Prepositions are words that indicate the temporal, logical or spatial relationship of their objects to the remaining sentence.

Table 8: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Preposition

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	We can listen music.	We can listen <u>to</u> music.
	02	We go <u>to</u> home.	We go home.
	03	She comes school at time.	She comes <u>to</u> school <u>on</u> time.
	04	He is three years senior <u>than</u> me.	He is three years senior <u>to</u> me.
O-	01	He wants to become a doctor serve the society.	He wants to become a doctor <u>to</u> serve the society.
	02	Nokia and Samsung both <u>of</u> the brands are	Nokia and Samsung both the brands are

Level	popular.	popular.
03	He settled <u>at</u> Pakistan.	He settled <u>in</u> Pakistan.
04	She is in the same school <u>from</u> 2018.	She is in the same school <u>since</u> 2018.

Articles

Articles are words that either particularise or generalise a noun. Such words are used with nouns to show the type of reference being made by nouns. There are two categories of articles in English. The first is Definite (The) and the second is Indefinite (a / an). The is used with particular nouns while a or an are used with common nouns.

Table 9: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Articles

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	It is not only a mobile phone but also <u>a</u> alarm and a calculator.	It is not only a mobile phone but also <u>an</u> alarm and a calculator.
	02	He is good student of our class.	He is <u>a</u> good student of our class.
	03	He is <u>a</u> intelligent boy.	He is <u>an</u> intelligent boy.
	04	He wears <u>a</u> simple clothes.	He wears simple clothes.
O-Level	01	I always wish <u>for</u> her successful life.	I always wish her <u>a</u> successful life.
	02	Nokia 8 is well-designed phone.	Nokia 8 is <u>a</u> well-designed phone.
	03	He is good student.	He is <u>a</u> good student.

Pronouns

A pronoun substitutes a noun by taking its place. Such words avoid tiresome repetition of nouns in sentences. There must be an agreement of pronoun with its antecedent. A pronoun must agree with its antecedent in number, case and gender.

Table 10: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Pronoun

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	<u>He</u> is a cheap mobile phone.	<u>It</u> is a cheap mobile phone.
	02	He takes interest in <u>our</u> books.	He takes interest in <u>his</u> books.
	03	On Sunday, <u>me</u> and Ali play games.	On Sunday, Ali and <u>I</u> play games.
	04	I am really proud of <u>them</u> .	I am really proud of <u>him</u> .
	05	I friends <u>which</u> are all caring.	I have friends <u>who</u> are all caring.
O-Level	01	In <u>these</u> days there was no facility of internet.	In <u>those</u> days there was no facility of internet.
	02	<u>Me</u> friends are special.	<u>My</u> friends are special.
	03	I have bought a new mobile phone. <u>It</u> RAM is 64 GB.	I have bought a new mobile phone. <u>Its</u> RAM is 64 GB.

Number (Singular/ Plural)

Number means whether a noun or pronoun is used in singular or plural form. There must be an agreement between a noun and pronoun in number. Likewise, a singular subject (noun / pronoun) takes a singular verb and a plural subject takes a plural verb.

Table 11: Errors Committed by SSC and O-Level Students in Number (Singular/ Plural)

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	Life is the bed of sorrows and <u>hardship</u> .	Life is the bed of sorrows and <u>hardships</u> .
	02	Man is social <u>animals</u> .	Man is a social <u>animal</u> .
	03	My friend helps poor <u>peoples</u> .	My friend helps poor <u>people</u> .
	04	She loves <u>childrens</u> .	She loves <u>children</u> .
	05	I have many <u>friend</u> .	I have many <u>friends</u> .
O-Level	01	Good <u>friend</u> are very rare.	Good <u>friends</u> are very rare.
	02	He helped me in finding different <u>locality</u> .	He helped me in finding different <u>localities</u> .
	03	Mobile <u>phones</u> is a useful device.	Mobile <u>phone</u> is a useful device.
	04	He has respect for <u>elder</u> .	He has respect for <u>elders</u> .
	14	Ali is a very good <u>students</u> .	Ali is a very good <u>student</u> .

Punctuations

Punctuation is the usage of particular marks that are added to writing in order to separate words, phrases, clauses or sentences. Its function is to show whether something is a statement, order, question etc.

Table 12: Errors Committed by SSC Students in Punctuation

Level	S. No	Error Identification	Error Correction
SSC	01	Mr_ Ali is my best friend.	Mr_ Ali is my best friend.
	02	I have lots of friends	I have lots of friends_
	03	Man is a thinking animal	Man is a thinking animal_
	04	May he live long_	May he live long!
	05	He is poor _but very talented.	He is poor but very talented.
O-Level	01	He is a great fan of Imran Khan_ The chairman of PTI.	He is a great fan of Imran Khan_ the chairman of PTI.
	02	Science has brought a revolution in every field of life_	Science has brought a revolution in every field of life_
	03	Later on the company launched smart phones.	Later on_ the company launched smart phones.
	04	However its market has declined.	However_ its market has declined.
	05	He is very dutiful	He is very dutiful_

Analysis of the SSC and O-Level Teachers' Interviews

Q. No.1: What errors do your students frequently commit in writing essays in English?

Table 13: The Responses of SSC Level Teachers

S. No	Errors	Frequency
01	Grammatical errors	36
02	The link of one paragraph with other.	8
03	Punctuation	29
04	Capitalization	32
05	To use the correct form of verb	13
06	Sentence structure	19
07	Presentation	3
08	Structural errors	4
09	To maintain the time and words limitation.	8
10	Correct sequence of tenses.	4
11	To forget the last letter of most of the words.	2

According to the table, most teachers at SSC level stated that grammatical errors, the errors in capitalization and punctuation were often committed by them. They also stated that to form a structurally correct sentence and to use the correct form of verbs were equally challenging for them. They also pointed out that to make the link of one paragraph with others was also difficult for them and they produced errors to link paragraphs with one another. The other errors which they mentioned were the errors in the presentation of ideas, structural errors, to maintain words and time limitation, to use the tenses in a correct sequence and to leave out the last letter of most of the words.

Table 14: The Responses of O-Level Teachers

S. No	Errors	Frequency
01	Grammatical errors	11
02	To use correct Punctuations.	10
03	Introductory and concluding lines	6
04	Capitalisation	4
05	Spelling	7
06	Vocabulary	4
07	Paragraph writing	3
08	Words repetition	2
09	Tenses errors	2

10	The use of pronouns	3
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As per the table above most of the students at O-Level stated that they committed errors in grammar and the correct use of punctuation marks. Spelling errors were also pointed out by a number of students. Some students mentioned that they made errors to write the introductory and concluding paragraphs in English essays. The errors of verb tense, pronouns, capitalization, incorrect use of vocabulary items and words repetition were also stated by them. Some of the students mentioned that they faced errors when writing paragraphs.

Q. No.2: What problems do you face while teaching English essay writing skills to your students?

Table 15: The Responses of SSC Teachers

S. No	Problems	Frequency
01	Weaknesses in grammar	18
02	Lack of vocabulary	15
03	Heavy classrooms	19
04	Students poor English background	11
05	Lack of knowledge regarding the various types of essays	3
06	Incorrect usage of words	5
07	Sentence construction errors	6
08	Lack of creativity	5
09	Poor ideas	6
10	The use of Grammar Translation Method(GTM)	2
11	Deficiency of focus	4
12	No concept Clarity	2
13	Weak understanding level of students	8
14	Lack of logical frame work	2
15	Teachers based approaches	2
16	Poor students response	4
17	No prior practice	5
18	Morphological problems	1

The table reveals that the major challenge for the teachers teaching at SSC level was the heavy and overloaded classrooms of the students due to which they could not cope with the weaknesses and shortcomings of their students. The second most problematic area for SSC level teachers was the students' low knowledge of grammar due to which they faced a lot of difficulties to inculcate in them effective essay writing skills. The problem, third in rank for SSC level teachers, was the insufficient vocabulary of the students. A number of the teachers were of the view that poor background knowledge of the students regarding English essay writing was also among the major problems that they faced during teaching English essay writing. Other challenging problems that SSC teachers highlighted were the inability of the students to generate new ideas, to use the right word on the right place, their lack of knowledge regarding the various types of essay, lack of creativity, errors in the construction of sentences, the use of Grammar translation Method (GTM), lack of focus and concentration, poor concepts and understanding level of the students, lack of a logical framework for essay, teachers centered approaches, poor response of the students, lack of ample practice as well as morphological problems.

Table 16: The Responses of O-Level Teachers

S. No	Problems	Frequency
01	First language interference	2
02	Weak academic background	3
03	To enable them to write introductory and concluding paragraphs.	3
04	The issues of coherence and cohesion	2
05	Weakness in sentence structure	2
06	Organization of essay	1
07	Lack of creativity	2
08	Poor expressions	1
09	Lack of vocabulary	3
10	Time management	1
11	Incorrect use of verbs	3
12	Weaknesses in grammar	2
13	Structure of essays	1
14	Illogical ideas	1

It is clear from the table that most of the teachers who taught at O-Level responded that due to the weak academic background of the students they faced problems to enable their students to write effective essays in English. They also highlighted that inculcating the skills for writing a good introduction and an impressive conclusion were also among the major problems that they encountered during their teaching. The students' lack of vocabulary and their low knowledge of syntax and the correct usage of verbs were also equally challenging for the teachers. The problems, second in rank, for the O-Level teachers were the first language interference, to maintain coherence and cohesion, lack of creativity on the part of the students and the weak grammatical background of the students. Some of the teachers opined that they faced problems to teach their students English essay writing strategies because the students were weak in the organization of essays, the expression of ideas, time management, and structure of essays and in organizing ideas.

Q.No.3: What do you think are the possible causes for the weaknesses in English essay writing of the students?

Table 17: The Responses of SSC Teachers

S. No	Causes	Frequency
01	Lack of practice	10
02	Less group work	11
03	Traditional teaching and learning methods	15
04	No feed back	4
05	No use of ICT	2
06	Weakness in grammar	7
07	Lack of knowledge regarding sentence structure	8
08	Product Approach	2
09	No wide reading habits	1
10	Limited vocabulary	4
11	Lack of Creativity	3
13	Absence of brainstorming	2
14	Weak primary knowledge	2
15	Lack of professional teachers	2
16	Lack of interest	2
19	Sentence formation	4
20	Absence of self study	4
21	Weak Punctuation	3
22	Poor language skills	4
23	Less individual practice	5
24	Cramming	2
25	Uneducated parents	1
26	No concept clarity	2
27	Spellings mistakes	6

The above table shows the responses of the SSC teachers regarding the causes responsible for the weaknesses in English essay writing of the students. Most of the teachers commented that less group work and lack of practice were the main causes due to which students were weak in English essay writing. A number of teachers responded that the use of traditional methods for teaching and learning was the main cause due to which students exhibited weaknesses in their written essays. The weak grammatical knowledge of the students was also considered to be a major cause for students' weaknesses. Other problems that SSC teachers pointed out were the absence of feedback on the part of the teachers, no use of Information Communication Technology (ICT), poor understanding of syntax, the use of Product Approach, no wide reading habits, limited vocabulary, lack of creativity, absence of brainstorming, weak background knowledge, lack of professionally trained teachers, lack of interest on the part of students, sentence formation, no self study, poor knowledge of punctuation, poor language skills, less individual practice, cramming, uneducated parents, no concept clarity and weak spelling.

Table 18: The Responses of O-Level Teachers

S. No	Causes	Frequency
01	Weak vocabulary	6
02	Weak syntax	6
03	No knowledge of essay structure	1
04	Varies from topic to topic	1
05	No wide reading	6

06	No thinking clarity	2
07	No brainstorming	1
08	No logical development	1
09	Weakness in grammar	3
10	Fear of writing	1
11	No prior knowledge	1
12	Ineffective teaching methodology	4
13	Traditional methods	1
14	Less practice	1

The statistics of the table shows that for O-Level teachers, among the main causes responsible for students' weaknesses in English essay writing were the insufficient vocabulary, poor syntax and lack of wide reading on the part of the students. Some of the teachers highlighted that ineffective teaching methodologies were the main cause responsible for students' weaknesses in essay writing. Other problems that O-Level teachers mentioned were the weak grammatical background, lack of clarity of thoughts, low knowledge of the structure of the essay, lack of thinking clarity, poor brainstorming skills, poor logical development of ideas, fear of writing, poor background knowledge, the use of traditional methods and lack of practice on the part of the students. Some teachers opined that causes for the weaknesses in English essay writing varies from topic to topic.

Conclusion

The findings of the study have manifested that the students of both SSC and O-Level in Pakistan have committed grammatical errors in writing essays in English. Subject-verb agreement, using correct verb tense and capitalisation were the most challenging areas for the students. They also committed errors in using articles, prepositions, pronouns, numbers and punctuation marks correctly. Moreover, some of the students were unable to construct meaningful sentences by using the words in a proper order. This study has also highlighted that students of both the grades in Pakistan had problems in writing introductory and concluding paragraphs and in maintaining cohesion and coherence in essays. However, SSC Level students committed more errors and manifested weak essay writing skills as compared to O-Level students, whose errors were fewer than SSC students, and who were comparatively found competent in composing effective essays. The possible causes for these weaknesses in essay writing had found to be poor academic background, fear of writing, first language interference, deficient vocabulary, cramming, lack of practice, using product approach and ignoring process approach, less group work, practicing traditional methodologies and lack of feedback to students. By identifying the errors in students' writing and stating the possible causes, the study can be beneficial to improve their weak areas and to enable them to get competency in writing. It can also assist ELT teachers in Pakistan in identifying the common errors and language problems in students' writing thereby enabling them to successfully cope with the errors and problems the students encounter by adopting effective teaching methodologies and practices in English classrooms in Pakistan.

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